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Assessment of Oxidative Potential in Culture Medium Conditioned by MCF7 Cancer Cells via FRAP and MDA Assay

Ahmadreza Gholamian, Hadi MohebAlian*, Mohammad Heidarpour

Department of Science, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Ferdowsi University, Mashhad, Iran

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*Corresponding author:

Hadi MohebAlian
Department of Science,
Faculty of Veterinary
Medicine, Ferdowsi
University, Mashhad, Iran.

E-mail address:

mohebalian@um.ac.ir

Abstract

Background and Aim: In recent years, the use of natural-origin drugs has gained significant attention due to their lower harmful effects compared to conventional chemical drugs. Recently, fungi and yeasts have been studied as rich sources of effective biological compounds. This research aims to investigate the oxidative effects of the cytoplasmic extract of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* on the MCF-7 cancer cell line. The objective of this study is to evaluate the antioxidant potential of this extract and analyze the changes in oxidative markers in these cells.

Materials and Methods: Yeast cells of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (PTCC 5052) were cultured, harvested, disrupted using sonication, and cytoplasmic fractions were extracted via ultracentrifugation. MCF7 breast cancer cells were cultured and treated with yeast cytoplasmic extract. The antioxidant potential (FRAP) and oxidative marker (MDA) were measured at different concentrations and time points using spectrophotometry. Statistical analyses were performed with SPSS version 28.

Results: The results of the FRAP and MDA tests indicate that, except for cases where the cells were treated for 72 hours, no significant differences were observed in other cases. Additionally, the normal distribution of the data can be observed using the qq.plot chart.

Conclusion: Additionally, in examining the antioxidant marker FRAP and the oxidative marker MDA, it was observed that there were no significant differences in the FRAP test between the control samples and the tested samples. Except for the 48 and 72-hour time points at a concentration of 2000 µg/ml, there was no considerable decrease compared to the control sample, making it impossible to conclusively determine that the reduction in this antioxidant marker caused cell death. Similarly, in the evaluation of the oxidative marker MDA, similar results were concluded.

Keywords: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, Breast cancer, Antioxidant activity

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Introduction

Cancer is the second leading cause of death globally and the sixth in Iran, with 143 new cancer cases per 100,000 Iranians annually [1]. One of the common cancers is breast cancer, the most prevalent non-skin malignancy and the second deadliest cancer among women in the United States, which becomes more common with age [2]. Although mortality from breast cancer has decreased due to early detection and better treatments, its prevalence continues to increase among African American and Hispanic populations. Risk factors such as family history, age, infertility, early puberty, obesity, external hormone use, smoking, and high-fat diets contribute to an increased risk of breast cancer. Research indicates that mutations in the BRCA1/BRCA2 genes are associated with disease recurrence. One effective treatment approach involves using plant-based substances [3]. One area of study is examining the oxidative effects of fungal extracts, including the cytoplasmic extract of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, on cancer cells. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, a unicellular yeast of the Ascomycota phylum, is known for its probiotic properties and use in bread making [4]. The FRAP (Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power) method is a fast, precise, and cost-effective technique for determining the total antioxidant capacity in various biological samples such as serum, plasma, urine, saliva, semen, cell lysates, milk, plant extracts, and more. Although modifications in the procedure and considerations are necessary when applying it to certain samples like milk, it remains one of the most commonly used methods in this field.

Principles: The FRAP method is based on the ability of antioxidants in biological samples to reduce Fe⁺³ ions to Fe⁺² ions. This reduction forms a ferrous ion complex with the TPTZ reagent, producing a blue-colored complex. The intensity of the blue color is measured at a wavelength of 593 nm. The total antioxidant capacity is reported in micromoles per liter (μmol/L) using ferrous sulfate as a standard, though Trolox may also be used as a standard, and the results can be reported as micromoles of Trolox equivalents [5].

MDA (Malondialdehyde) causes disturbances in cell membrane function. The analysis of MDA is a very useful indicator for demonstrating lipid peroxidation, which involves cellular dysfunction. Cells capable of producing reactive oxygen species (ROS) include inflammatory cells, fibroblasts, endothelial cells, and osteoclasts. The final product of these processes is free radicals, which have a low molecular weight. MDA analysis is the most commonly used method for assessing increased lipid peroxidation [6].

This study aims to assess the oxidative markers FRAP and MDA in untreated and treated MCF-7 cell lines with the fungal extract of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Material and Methods

Extracting Cytoplasmic Fractions from Saccharomyces cerevisiae (PTCC 5052)

The standard strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (PTCC 5052) was obtained from the fungal culture collection of the Mycology Department, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Urmia University. Yeast cells were cultured on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) containing the antibiotic chloramphenicol and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After preparing fresh, pure yeast cultures, the cells were transferred to YPG liquid medium (composed of glucose: 20 g/L, peptone: 20 g/L, yeast extract: 10 g/L, dissolved in 1 liter of distilled water) supplemented with chloramphenicol for scaling up. The cultures were incubated at 30°C in a shaker incubator at 130 rpm for 72 hours. Yeast cells were then harvested by refrigerated centrifugation at 4500 rpm for 5 minutes. The collected cells were washed three times with sterile distilled water using centrifugation at 2500 rpm for 15 minutes. For cell disruption, a sonicator device was utilized. A suspension of yeast cells was prepared in cold 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH = 7.2) and subjected to sonication. The

samples were placed in a sonicator tube, and cell disruption was performed at 60% amplitude for 2 minutes. Following complete cell lysis, cell wall debris was removed by refrigerated centrifugation at 12,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. The resulting supernatant was further processed for cytoplasmic extraction using ultracentrifugation at 100,000 rpm for 1 hour. The final supernatant, containing the cytoplasmic extract, was collected into separate tubes and subjected to dialysis using dialysis membranes.

Cell Culture

Breast cancer (MCF7) cells were obtained from the Pasteur Institute Cell Bank, delivered frozen in a cryotube, and stored in a liquid nitrogen tank until needed for cultivation. To thaw the cells, the cryotube was removed from the nitrogen tank and placed in a 37°C water bath for 1 minute, then sterilized and transferred under a laminar flow hood. The hood was disinfected with ethanol-soaked cotton, and tools were also sterilized with ethanol. To prepare 50 mL of culture medium, 44.5 mL RPMI medium, 0.5 mL penicillin-streptomycin (Pen-Strep), and 5 mL fetal bovine serum (FBS) were added to a sterile 50-mL Falcon tube. The thawed cells were diluted with 1 mL of culture medium, transferred to a sterile 15-mL Falcon tube, and centrifuged at $300 \times g$ for 5 minutes to remove DMSO. The supernatant was discarded, and fresh medium was added to the cell pellet. The cells were resuspended, transferred to a sterile cell culture flask, and placed in an incubator to support growth. The medium was replaced daily or every other day depending on nutrient consumption, indicated by the color change to yellow or cloudy. After 5 days, the cells reached confluency, covering the flask surface, and were split into multiple flasks to prevent detachment and cell death. The process involved centrifugation, removal of old medium, and addition of fresh medium, after which the cells were transferred into two sterile culture flasks, each containing 6 mL of RPMI with FBS and Pen-Strep, and returned to the incubator. Cell growth and proliferation were regularly monitored using an inverted microscope to ensure optimal conditions.

Measurement of Oxidative Index (FRAP)

To measure the total antioxidant potential of the medium using the FRAP method, the Benzie and Strain protocol was employed. For this assay, cells were treated with the cytoplasmic extract of the target fungus at three concentrations (500, 1000, and 2000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and at three time points (24, 48, and 72 hours). The FRAP working solution was prepared as follows: 10 mL of acetate buffer was mixed with 1 mL of TPTZ solution (prepared in hydrochloric acid), followed by the addition of 1 mL of ferric chloride solution. After preparation, 1.5 mL of this solution was transferred into a cuvette, heated to 37°C, and its absorbance was measured at 593 nm. Next, 50 μL of the test samples were added to the prepared solution to initiate the reaction. Changes in absorbance at 593 nm were recorded at 37°C over 4 minutes. The FRAP value was determined by subtracting the blank absorbance from the sample absorbance.

Measurement of MDA as an Oxidative Marker

MDA levels were measured in the culture medium, with cells treated with yeast cytoplasmic extract at concentrations of 2000, 1000, and 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for 24, 48, and 72 hours. The assay was performed according to the methods of Hadley and Draper. A mixture of 0.67% thiobarbituric acid and 20% trichloroacetic acid was prepared and incubated at 100°C for 20 minutes. Following incubation, the samples were centrifuged at $12,000 \times g$ for 5 minutes. The resulting color, formed by the reaction between MDA and thiobarbituric acid, was quantified using a spectrophotometer at 533 nm.

Data Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 28. Descriptive statistics were first used to summarize the data. Subsequently, repeated measures ANOVA was applied to test the

research hypotheses.

Results

The total antioxidant potential of the culture medium was assessed by FRAP assay. The results showed no significant changes, except when the cells were exposed to the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cytoplasmic extract for 72 hours (Figure 1). In the majority of cases, no substantial differences in total antioxidant potential were detected relative to the control group, suggesting that the cytoplasmic extract did not markedly enhance the antioxidant capacity of the medium under most conditions. MCF7 cells were divided into a control group (untreated) and treatment groups exposed to the cytoplasmic extract at concentrations of 500, 1000, and 2000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Statistical analysis, employing a normal quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plot of the residuals, indicated a normal distribution of the data, validating the use of parametric statistical methods (Figure 2). Specifically, the p-value was greater than 0.05, confirming the normal distribution of the residuals.

Figure 1. Results of the FRAP assay, showing the total antioxidant potential of the culture medium after treatment with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cytoplasmic extract at various concentrations (500, 1000, and 2000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and time points (24, 48, and 72 hours). The control group (0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) is also represented. * indicates significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to control group.

Figure 2. Normal Q-Q Plot for FRAP Test. This plot assesses the normality of residuals from the FRAP assay data across all treatment groups and the control group.

Evaluation of the oxidative marker MDA revealed no significant changes across varying concentrations (500, 1000, and 2000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and time points (24, 48, and 72 hours) when compared to the control group (Figure 3). This suggests that the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cytoplasmic extract did not induce significant lipid peroxidation in MCF7 cells under the tested conditions. Similar to the FRAP assay, statistical analysis, using a normal quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plot of the residuals, confirmed a normal distribution of the residuals (Figure 4). The alignment of points around a straight line in the Q-Q plot visually supports the normality assumption, with a p-value greater than 0.05. Therefore, it is unlikely that cell death is due to changes in this oxidative marker.

Figure 3. Normal Q-Q Plot for FRAP Test. This plot assesses the normality of residuals from the FRAP assay data across all treatment groups and the control group.

Figure 4. Results of the MDA Test, illustrating the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) in the culture medium after treatment with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cytoplasmic extract at various concentrations (500, 1000, and 2000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and time points (24, 48, and 72 hours). The control group (0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) is also represented.

Discussion

Cancer, second only to cardiovascular diseases, is considered one of the most significant health challenges worldwide. Among the various types of cancer, breast cancer is one of the most prevalent. Numerous conventional treatments have been developed and implemented to combat cancer; however, many of these treatments are associated with considerable side effects, including mortality. Due to the adverse effects of chemical-based therapies, there has been a growing interest in plant-based and fungal-based medicines. These alternative treatments offer potential therapeutic

benefits with fewer harmful effects compared to chemotherapy, which has contributed to their increasing popularity [7].

The findings of this study indicate that the culture medium conditioned by MCF7 cells did not significantly alter oxidative potential. The absence of observable changes in the measured indices (FRAP and MDA) could be attributed to several factors. One possible explanation is the inherent stability of MCF7 cells within the culture medium. These cells are widely utilized as a cancer model in numerous studies, and one of their distinguishing characteristics is their ability to maintain stability under varying environmental conditions. This stability may account for the lack of oxidative changes observed in this study. Additionally, the sensitivity of the FRAP and MDA assays may be insufficient to detect subtle oxidative variations under the specified conditions, suggesting that the use of more sensitive assays could yield different results. Furthermore, environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and nutrient concentration within the culture medium may not have been substantial enough to induce noticeable changes in oxidative potential. Further investigations employing a range of assays and environmental conditions are warranted to advance the understanding of oxidative mechanisms in MCF7 cancer cells.

The MCF7 cell line has not been extensively studied within the context of the present investigation, and the effects of this yeast remain insufficiently explored. Nonetheless, a significant body of research has employed plant extracts, yeast and fungal cell wall extracts, cytoplasmic extracts, and bacterial extracts to examine the anticancer properties of these substances across various cancer cell lines, particularly breast cancer and the MCF7 cell line. In a study conducted by Javadi and colleagues in 2022, the anticancer effects of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Digitalis nevrosa* on the MCF7 breast cancer cell line were evaluated. The findings demonstrated a dose-dependent effect on cell viability, with the 50% lethal concentration (LC50) determined to be 39.45 micrograms per milliliter. Furthermore, the IC50 concentration influenced the expression of the genes P53, Bax, Bcl2, and CDH1, resulting in alterations relative to the control gene [8]. Similarly, a study by Firoozeh Niazvand in 2019 investigated the impact of nanoparticles loaded with quercetin on human breast cancer cells (MCF7). The results indicated that these nanoparticles significantly enhanced apoptosis while simultaneously increasing the production of reactive oxygen species. Additionally, the nanoparticles contributed to a 50% reduction in cancer cell growth [9]. Pirouz Panah and colleagues (2015) conducted a study examining the effects of silibinin on gene expression (P53), cell proliferation, and apoptosis in the MCF7 cell line. The results demonstrated that silibinin induced a reduction in cell growth and promoted apoptosis in a dose- and time-dependent manner. Additionally, silibinin treatment upregulated the expression of the P53 gene, suggesting its potential role as an anti-breast cancer agent by facilitating cell death through the apoptosis pathway [10]. Another study by Ravi Subbiah and Abplanalp (2003) assessed the effects of sterol extracted from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* on breast cancer cells. The study revealed that the active compound induced apoptosis and demonstrated anti-tumor activities over time [11]. Furthermore, Qiu Wu and colleagues (2018) investigated the inhibitory effects of quercetin and its derivatives—isorhamnetin and isorhamnetin-3-glucuronide—on the proliferation of MCF7 human breast cancer cells. The study concluded that these compounds initiated apoptosis during the early phase and promoted the generation of reactive oxygen species. However, further research is necessary to elucidate their molecular properties [12].

Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the effects of the active substance on the selected parameters, and the results indicated that no significant changes were observed in the levels of the two indices

compared to the control sample. Among the notable findings, the FRAP test demonstrated a discernible effect at a concentration of 2000 after 48 and 72 hours. However, in other cases, the observed changes relative to the control sample were minimal. Similarly, in the MDA test, a significant change was detected at the concentration of 2000 after 24 hours, while in other instances, no substantial changes were noted. Furthermore, statistical analysis confirmed that the data followed a normal distribution. Therefore, it can be concluded that the extracted substance did not induce any considerable alterations in the evaluated indices, suggesting that these indices do not significantly influence cell viability or non-viability.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests.

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